

A Journal of Clinical Dentistry

Open Access Full Text Article

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery and its Ethical Challenges: A Review

Parityancha Bansal¹
 Asmita Sharma²
 Ramandeep Singh Brar³
 Gursimrat Brar⁴
 Jasmine⁵

PG Student¹
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab

PG Student²
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab

Professor & Head³
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab

Professor⁴
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab

Associate Professor⁵
 Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
 Dasmesh Institute of Research & Dental Sciences
 Faridkot, Punjab

Submitted 16 September 2025
 Accepted 28 October 2025
 Published xx xxx xxxx

Access this Article Online Website: www.healtalk.in	Quick Response Code
DOI	

Abstract

The field of artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a versatile health technology tool revolutionizing medical field over the past two decades. AI encompasses different concepts such as machine learning, neural networks and deep learning techniques that present a broad spectrum of purposes to assist surgeons with diagnosis, preoperative planning, therapeutic decisions as well as outcome prediction and evaluation. AI carries potential to advance the field of OMFS and generate novel solution for persisting clinical challenges. This algorithm should, however, be precisely evaluated clinically, and a systematic ethical consideration should be given regarding data protection and transparency. The purpose of this review is to present a comprehensive summary of the existing scientific knowledge of AI and describe its current and future applications in maxillofacial surgery.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery; Deep learning; Machine learning

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science which can be defined as a sequence of operations (software) designed to perform a specific task.¹ The term Artificial Intelligence was coined by John McCarthy, a mathematician, in 1955. MYCIN system (1980s) was the first AI implemented in healthcare that was trained to distinguish various bacterial infections.²

In medicine the most commonly used branch of AI is machine learning and, more recently, deep learning. Machine learning (ML) is a branch in which systems learn to perform intelligent tasks without prior knowledge of the given subject. Instead, the systems identify patterns from a large dataset without any human assistance.³ Deep learning (DL) is a sub-branch of ML wherein systems attempt to learn pattern as well as hierarchy of composable patterns that build on each other. An extremely popular class of DL algorithms is the artificial neural network (ANN) which is a structure composed of many small communicating units called neurons organized in layers. In medicine, one of the most commonly used subclasses of ANN is the convolutional neural network (CNN) which uses a special neuron connection architecture and the mathematical operation, convolution, to process digital signals such as image, sound and video.⁴

AI is a rapidly evolving field that has made remarkable advancements in various health-care specialties and has potential to revolutionize the ways of diagnosis, treatment planning, therapeutic decisions, and post-operative evaluation in OMFS. By using advanced algorithms AI systems analyze complex imaging data, such as CT scans and 3D models, to aid in preoperative assessments, virtual surgical simulations, and personalized treatment plans. Further, AI can also assist surgeons in intraoperative decision making by providing real time guidance and feedback, improving surgical accuracy, and decreasing complications.⁵

How to Cite This Article : Bansal et al. -

In this review article, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the diverse applications of AI in OMFS by analyzing recent advancements, challenges, and future prospects.

Radiographic Image Quality Improvement

Poor quality of radiographic image due to distinct interferences can interfere with the diagnostic process. Deep learning techniques have shown great potential in overcoming the limitations of conventional methods. AI has been employed in CT and CBCT images to reduce motion artifacts caused by patient or organ movements and metal artifacts. These artifacts can negatively impact the accuracy of diagnostic procedures.⁶

Diagnosis of Cysts and Tumors

Appropriate classification and diagnosis of various cysts and tumors of oral and maxillofacial region pose challenges for surgeons. Abdolali et al. proposed a model that uses asymmetry analysis to automatically segment radicular cysts, dentigerous cysts, and odontogenic keratocysts in CBCT images.⁷ Rana et al. employed a surgical navigation program to segment keratocysts and measure their volume and concluded that the results were comparable with that of more established methods.⁸ Santer et al. in a systematic review including 13 studies, found that AI carries promising potential in detecting suspicious lymph nodes in patients with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma with a mean accuracy of 86%.⁹

Orthognathic Surgery

Traditional surgical planning methods utilizing radiographs and models have limitations, especially for patients with extensive facial asymmetry. AI can be used to identify precise landmarks, analyze digital cephalometric data, make clinical decisions, and predict treatment outcomes using software enabled by AI.⁵ Hong et al. in a study reported the accuracy of AI assisted cephalometric landmark detection in jaw orthognathic surgery cases to be 75%.¹⁰ A study by Jeong et al. reported that CNN was able to accurately diagnose surgical patients based on facial photographs of frontal and lateral profile.¹¹

Rhinoplasty

There are lots of technical challenges associated with rhinoplasty owing to its complexity and significant aesthetic and functional concern for the patient. A machine learning algorithm (ML) can recognize hidden patterns and accurately predict outcomes.⁵ Zeng et al. developed a virtual planning system to correctly estimate the dimensions of forehead flaps to be raised for nasal defect reconstruction through a combination of 3D image registration technology.¹² Chinski et al. developed an AI model that accurately simulates the outcomes of rhinoplasty surgeries with the help of perioperative photographs.¹³

Robotic Surgery in OMFS

Within the field of OMFS, AI has found application in robotic surgery. AI-aided surgical procedures, including dental implants, tumor resections, biopsies, and TMJ surgeries, have demonstrated successful and more precise results. Research has shown that use of AI improved the accuracy and safety of dental implant procedures as compared to conventional techniques and reduced the need for revision surgeries in some cases.¹⁴ Moreover, AI-aided approaches have shown to enable more precise surgical resection of tumors and cysts, minimizing the requirement for adjunctive methods.¹⁵

Other uses- AI has also shown promise in improving efficiency amongst surgeons. It has shown to play a role in automated diagnosis making based on radiology, automated updates of patient records and improve patient safety by detecting drug interactions. This may improve efficiency for surgeons; however, there may be

issues regarding accuracy of automated diagnosis based on radiology that still needs further refinement.⁵

Discussion: AI has made a significant impact within the field of OMFS in the past decade. This review analyzed the latest literature regarding use of AI in OMFS and found various applications within the field including radiographic image quality improvement, diagnosis of tumors/cysts, preoperative planning in orthognathic surgery, automated diagnosis making based on radiographic findings, automated update of patient records, detection of drug interactions etc.

Although AI holds promising potential in OMFS, several challenges need to be addressed for its successful execution. The sharing of clinical data and its management are major challenges in the application of AI systems in healthcare department. Personal data of patients are necessary for initial training of AI algorithms and its improvement. To integrate AI into clinical scenarios, systems must be adapted to protect patients' privacy.¹⁶ Therefore, before considering broader implementation, personal data has to be anonymized.¹⁷

Mechanisms must be created to control the quality of the algorithms used as AI systems are associated with safety issues. To rectify this situation, the United States Food and Drug Administration has created a new drug category- "Software as Medical Device," which regulates safe innovation and patient safety. Furthermore, the quality of predictions performed by AI systems depends on the accuracy of annotations of the dataset used in initial training. Poorly labeled data will lead to poor results which is a substantial issue. Obscure accountability in the use of AI systems is another concern as to who will be held responsible for a patient who encounters unintentional consequences that may result from an error caused by the AI technology.¹⁸

Future directions include further development of AI based decision support systems, robotic assisted surgeries, and virtual reality technology in OMFS. AI will continue to assist the surgeon in the decision making process by providing information that would otherwise be difficult to gather and compare.¹⁹ The role of the surgeon is not threatened in the short term, but we must make an effort to interpret the suggestions that arise from AI.²⁰

Conclusion: Use of AI should be viewed as an adjunct to assist surgeons. Taking into consideration the current limitations, developing the AI model can assist surgeons in decision making and provide an additional tool for future diagnosis and treatment planning in Oral and Maxillofacial surgeries. It is crucial to ensure that AI is integrated in a safe and controlled manner. Identifying the study gaps will require more clinical research with use of AI by incorporating larger sample sizes, cross-validation, and inter-model comparisons.

References

1. Muller J, Massaron L. Artificial intelligence for dummies. Hoboken, N.J.: John Wiley & Sons; 2018.
2. Swartout, W.R., 1985. Rule based expert systems: The mycin experiments of the stanford heuristic programming project: BG Buchanan and EH Shortliffe, (addison-wesley, reading, ma, 1984); 702 pages, \$40.50.
3. Nguyen, T.T., Larrivée, N., Lee, A., Bilaniuk, O. and Durand, R., 2021. Use of artificial intelligence in dentistry: current clinical trends and research advances. J Can Dent Assoc, 87(17), pp. 1488-2159.
4. Nielsen, M.A., 2015. Neural networks and deep learning (Vol. 25, pp. 15-24). San Francisco, CA, USA: Determination press.
5. Rokhshad, R.; Keyhan, S.O.; Yousefi, P. Artificial intelligence

- applications and ethical challenges in oral and maxillofacial cosmetic surgery: A narrative review. *Maxillofac. Plast. Reconstr. Surg.* 2023, 45, 14.
6. Hyun, C.M.; Bayarara, T.; Yun, H.S.; Jang, T.J.; Park, H.S.; Seo, J.K. Deep learning method for reducing metal artifacts in dental cone beam CT using supplementary information from intra-oral scan. *Phys. Med. Biol.* 2022, 67, 175007
 7. Abdolali, F., Zoroofi, R.A., Otake, Y. and Sato, Y., 2016. Automatic segmentation of maxillofacial cysts in cone beam CT images. *Computers in biology and medicine*, 72, pp.108-119.
 8. Rana, M., Modrow, D., Keuchel, J., Chui, C., Rana, M., Wagner, M. and Gellrich, N.C., 2015. Development and evaluation of an automatic tumor segmentation tool: a comparison between automatic, semi-automatic and manual segmentation of mandibular odontogenic cysts and tumors. *Journal of Cranio-Maxillofacial Surgery*, 43 (3), pp.355-359.
 9. Santer, M., Kloppenburg, M., Gottfried, T.M., Runge, A., Schmutzhard, J., Vorbach, S.M., Mangesius, J., Riedl, D., Mangesius, S., Widmann, G. and Riechelmann, H., 2022. Current applications of artificial intelligence to classify cervical lymph nodes in patients with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma a systematic review. *Cancers*, 14 (21), p.5397.
 10. Hong, M., Kim, I., Cho, J.H., Kang, K.H., Kim, M., Kim, S.J., Kim, Y.J., Sung, S.J., Kim, Y.H., Lim, S.H. and Kim, N., 2022. Accuracy of artificial intelligence assisted landmark identification in serial lateral cephalograms of Class III patients who underwent orthodontic treatment and two jaw orthognathic surgery. *Korean Journal of Orthodontics*, 52 (4), pp.287-297.
 11. Jeong, S.H., Yun, J.P., Yeom, H.G., Lim, H.J., Lee, J. and Kim, B.C., 2020. Deep learning based discrimination of soft tissue profiles requiring orthognathic surgery by facial photographs. *Scientific Reports*, 10 (1), p.16235.
 12. Zeng, W., Chen, G., Ju, R., Yin, H., Tian, W. and Tang, W., 2018. The combined application of database and three dimensional image registration technology in the restoration of total nose defect. *Journal of Craniofacial Surgery*, 29(5), pp.e484-e487.
 13. Chinski, H., Lerch, R., Tournour, D., Chinski, L. and Caruso, D., 2021. An artificial intelligence tool for image simulation in rhinoplasty. *Facial Plastic Surgery*, 38 (02), pp.201-206.
 14. Jaemsuwan, S., Arunjaroensuk, S., Kaboosaya, B., Subbalekha, K., Mattheos, N. and Pimkhaokham, A., 2023. Comparison of the accuracy of implant position among freehand implant placement, static and dynamic computer assisted implant surgery in fully edentulous patients: a non-randomized prospective study. *International Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*, 52 (2), pp.264-271.
 15. Balaban, C., Inam, W., Kennedy, R. and Faiella, R., 2021. The Future of Dentistry: How AI is Transforming Dental Practices. *Compendium of Continuing Education in Dentistry (Jamesburg, NJ: 1995)*, 42 (1), pp.14-17.
 16. Char, D.S., Shah, N.H. and Magnus, D., 2018. Implementing machine learning in health care addressing ethical challenges. *The New England journal of medicine*, 378 (11), p.981.
 17. He, J., Baxter, S.L., Xu, J., Xu, J., Zhou, X. and Zhang, K., 2019. The practical implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in medicine. *Nature medicine*, 25(1), pp.30-36.
 18. Software as medical device (SaMD). Maryland: United States Food & Drug Administration; 2018.
 19. Chen, Y.W., Stanley, K. and Att, W., 2020. Artificial intelligence in dentistry: current applications and future perspectives. *Quintessence Int*, 51(3), pp.248-257.
 20. Muñoz-Guerra Mario Fernando. Artificial intelligence in maxillofacial surgery. Future or present?. *Rev Esp Cirug Oral y Maxilofac [Internet]*. 2022 June [cited 2024 Jan 13]; 44(2): 53-55. Available from: http://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1130-05582022000200001&lng=en. Epub Oct 17, 2022. <https://dx.doi.org/10.20986/recom.2022.1372/2022>.

Heal Talk- Promoting Preventive Care For Lifelong Smiles